

Use case fact-sheet

Actors

List all actors involved in the Use Case and the Geographic Information-related processes they are involved in, then put a “x” in correspondence to the relevant cells.

Who (actor) ²	What (Action) ¹					
	Data acquisition/creation	Data analysis/processing/validation	Data publication	Extraction of information from published data	Data maintenance	xxx
Municipality			x			
Data providers	x	x				
Decision makers					x	
Officers/technicians		x	x	x	x	
Researchers				x		
General Public						

Table 1: Overview of the actors involved in the Use Case

Use Case (UC) main info	
Identifier	GR_UHI
Name	Graz UHI
Description	Based on ground data and the temperature information from aerial thermal images, the reliability of temperature measurements from satellite analysis is assessed.
Primary User	Technicians and urban planners
Goal	To assess the quality of the analysis done on UHI estimated from satellite image analysis (free data)
Owner	FBK (to be discussed)
Status	Tool and data metadata completed Tools implementation completed
Policy context	
Challenges & Priorities	Climate change amplifies existing challenges in Graz which result from the combination of different factors. One challenge is high temperatures in densely built areas, namely Urban Heat Islands (UHI). Those areas are in

¹ Add new processes or rename the existing ones or split the ones currently merged as you may find more appropriate

² Add new actors or rename the existing ones

	<p><i>the inner-city/old town and densely built areas around the inner city quarter (about 2,5km²), especially in big places or along major streets without much vegetation. The urban climate analysis has shown maximum temperature differences of about 10K (Kelvin) or 2,5 K mean temperature difference between the densely built inner city and the cold valleys in the east of Graz. In combination with a more frequent occurrence of hot days (= days with temperatures over 30°C), the UHI-effect is even stronger. Thermal satellite images are available for free and represent important data for UHI estimation and climate change monitoring.</i></p>
<p>Strategy/Plan/Regulation</p>	<p>C Adaptation Action Plan describes plausible climate change effects for the people, infrastructure, and nature in Graz and provides measures for 11 pressing topics (Stadt Graz – Umweltamt, 2018).</p> <p>To counteract the effect of UHI, the Plan aims to foster the expansion of urban green areas. Specifically the city sets up to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>maintain and increase the number of green spaces in the city ensuring biodiversity, plant more drought-resistant plants, secure and expand the tree population, implement small green spaces and create open water areas.</i> ● <i>Use of the Stockholm system which offers a practical and (cost) effective solution for planting trees in hard landscaped areas.</i> ● <i>Utilising digital urban climate analyses, the city can estimate and compare the effectiveness of specific countermeasures to reduce the effects of UHIs. The data which maps UHIs in the city should be made available to citizens.</i> <p><i>The Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan 2020 / 2040 consists of two parts regarding (1) strategic guidelines for planning and political decision-making and (2) the action/measures program with specific recommendations for various locations in town.</i></p>
<p>Local Green Deal / City contract(s)</p>	<p><i>Urban development concept 4.0 STEK (2013). The 4.0 STEK is an essential tool for the urban planning office, as it sets goals on how the city should develop within the next 15 years following 10 principles. To support urban planning and development considering adaptation and mitigation action, since September 2020 the city of Graz is developing the Klimainformationssystem (KIS), (climate information system) which will play a major role in monitoring, modelling, visualising and predicting relevant climate change data. The development of KIS is to support city departments with reliable, up-to-date data as a basis for future-proof decisions and transparent communication with city stakeholders. According to different principles of STEK 4.0 and the five parts of the Plan, this use case can support:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>The compliance with Principle 3 of the Plan according to which urban planning should take a holistic approach, e.g. maintain a green belt, create public green spaces and ensure diversity throughout the city, keeping all stakeholders in mind and ensuring a healthy climate</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measures to Increase green spaces like parks, playgrounds and sports fields throughout the city (10. Grundsatz) • The adherence to “Freihaltezone”, areas that are to remain empty and cannot be used as building areas. Instead, these areas should be used to build or maintain parks and similar green spaces • The creation of green corridors that includes empty land, forest and urban areas with low building density. • Planting of new roadside greenery • Increase of tree density in the city • Ensure that new buildings have big enough green space that is accessible to all tenants (aiming for 20% of the total building area). <p><i>In March and April 2021 residents of Graz could submit ideas for a more livable Graz, which could be implemented with the funds from the so-called citizen’s budget. Among the most popular ideas were several climate-related projects, also taking into account presence of green in the urban area and its accessibility. Among them:</i></p> <p><i>SAVE THE BEES (€100,000): Planting of flower meadows on urban green spaces and establishment of three apiary areas in cooperation with beekeepers;</i></p> <p><i>WILDFLOWER MEADOWS FOR GRAZ (€100,000): Planting of about 10,000 m2 wildflower meadows in urban green spaces;</i></p> <p><i>MARGARETENBAD FRONT GARDEN ((€100,000): Redesigning and greening the front garden of the Margaretenbad, including replacing the concrete by green areas ;</i></p> <p><i>TREES IN THE CITY CENTER ((€100,000): Planting of extra trees in the area of Harrachgasse (Geidorf district)</i></p> <p><i>CITY’S FOREST AREAS (€50,000): Preservation and extension of the forest areas in the city.</i></p>
<p>European Green Deal Policy Area</p>	<p>This use case contributes to increasing the EU’s climate ambition for 2030 and 2050; and achieving the priorities related to climate adaptation. The EU Strategy for Adaptation sets both the framework for achieving climate neutrality and the ambition on adaptation by 2050. The implementation of these actions aims to respond to the needs of adaptation to climate change at the local level and the reduction of the impact of increasingly persistent hazards such as the rising urban temperatures.</p>
<p>Precondition</p>	
<p><i>Acquisition of meteorological data (done)</i></p> <p><i>Acquisition of 3D geometric models (done)</i></p> <p><i>Information on roof and ground materials (done)</i></p> <p><i>Aerial image analysis (done)</i></p> <p><i>Satellite image analysis (done)</i></p>	
<p>Postcondition</p>	

DRI (Decision Ready Information)	<p><i>Technical report with description of method and results of the analysis between temperature estimation based on satellite and aerial images</i></p> <p><u>Graz - Quality of LST from satellite thermal images using aerial thermal images as reference</u></p>
Use of DRI	<p><i>Technicians in the municipality can interpret the UHI information from satellite image analysis with awareness of the product accuracy</i></p>
Use case processing steps	
<p><i>Insert the link to the BPMN representation of the use case</i></p> <p><u>https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1Rh9XaQDOldJU7EESaweYbgFqQ-8vVyQD</u></p>	
DOI to processing steps BPMN	
<p><u>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15167436</u></p>	